

Equilibrium Study of Mixed Complexes of Uranyl Ion with Pyridine Carboxylic Acids as Primary and Some Dicarboxylic Acids as Secondary Ligands*

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Equilibrium constants of the binary and ternary complexes of UO_2^{2+} with pyridine carboxylic acids and some dicarboxylic acids have been investigated by pH titration method at 30° and $\mu = 0.1 M$ ($NaClO_4$). Pyridine carboxylic acids used are picolinic, quinolinic, dipicolinic and dicarboxylic acids are malic, maleic, chlorosuccinic, dimercapto succinic, methylmalonic and dimethylmalonic. UO_2^{2+} forms 1:1 and 1:2 binary bis complexes with all the ligand acids except maleic, chlorosuccinic and dimercapto succinic.

Ternary chelates of UO_2^{2+} -pyridine carboxylic-secondary acid systems have been studied. Binary stabilities are explained on the ring size effect and nature of substituent in the parent acids. Equilibrium constants of ternary complexes were utilized to discuss the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary. The values of K_{2YX} and β_{XY} depend on the basicities of the secondary ligands and 1:1 binary stabilities of the metal chelates respectively.

THERE has been appreciable interest in UO_2^{2+} -complexes with various organic ligands¹⁻³. The ability of the UO_2^{2+} ion to react with poly functional ligands containing carboxylic groups to give complex species of various kinds has been established by several authors^{4,5}. In the course of our studies on mixed-ligand complexes of metal ions with various ligands, we have earlier reported the formation of series of mixed-ligand complexes with bidentate ligands such as amino acids, 2,2'-bipyridyl, thiodicarboxylic and simple dicarboxylic acids⁶⁻⁹. However, although several studies of mixed complexes of UO_2^{2+} ion have been published,^{10,11} no data are to date available for the mixed-ligand complexes of UO_2^{2+} ion with pyridine carboxylic and substituted succinic and malonic acids. It therefore seemed desirable to obtain some information about the complexing ability of the substituted dicarboxylic acids with 1:1 UO_2^{2+} -pyridine carboxylate complex, particularly from the stand point of metal-ligand interactions and to describe the preferential formation of ternary complexes.

Experimental

The ligands such as picolinic, quinolinic and dipicolinic, chlorosuccinic, dimercapto succinic, malic,

maleic, methyl malonic and dimethyl malonic acids were of Fluka (Germany) and B.D.H. (AnalaR) quality. These ligands were purified by recrystallization and purity was checked by their melting points. Uranyl nitrate (AnalaR), quality was dissolved in perchloric acid to give required concentration. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The details of the other chemicals and measurements of pH were same as described in the preceding paper^{1,2} and outlined in our earlier papers^{1,3,14}.

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation constants of the ligands and stability constants of uranyl complexes (Table-1) were calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti,^{15,16}. The formation of mixed ligand chelate was initially proved by qualitative evidence and the method of Carey and Martell¹⁷ was used to probe in to nature of mixed-ligand. The mixed-ligand stabilities and other equilibrium constants were evaluated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Manning¹⁸. The formation of simple and mixed species of uranyl complexes was the same and relevant equilibria are discussed in the preceding paper^{1,2}.

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TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS ($pK \pm 0.01 - 0.04$) OF LIGANDS AND STABILITY CONSTANTS ($\log K$) OF URANYL COMPLEXES.

Ligand/acids	$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$		Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ C$	
	Dissociation constants pK_1	pK_2	stability constants $\log K_2$	$\log \bar{K}_2$
Picolinic	1.66 (1.66)	5.24 (5.23)	4.46	3.75
Quinolinic	2.35 (2.36)	4.71 (4.72)	4.65 ^a	3.65 ^a
Dipicolinic	2.11 (2.10)	4.83 (4.76)	5.44	5.24
Succinic ^b	3.82 (3.86)	5.22 (5.22)	4.48	—
Malonic ^c	2.66 (2.68)	5.28 (5.27)	5.56	3.80
Malic	3.22 (3.22)	4.78 (4.78)	5.50 (5.50)	3.63 (3.63)
Maleic	1.95 (1.95) ^d	6.16 (6.16) ^d	5.15 (5.15) ^d	—
Chlorosuccinic	2.46	4.41	3.57	—
Dimercaptosuccinic	2.56	4.22	3.06	—
Methylmalonic	2.98 (2.97)	5.65 (5.46)	6.70	4.22
Dimethylmalonic	3.02 (3.08)	6.03 (5.81)	6.32	4.05

Bracket values from reference 3.

a = ref. 19, b = ref. 8, c = ref. 21, d = ref. 22.

$\log K_1$ and $\log \bar{K}_2$ values were calculated by the method of Least Squares.

In most of cases the dissociation constants are close to the values reported in literature but the values differ for different experimental conditions. The observed lower values of dissociation constants in chlorosuccinic acid is due to the electron withdrawing inductive effect of chlorine. The effect is certainly reduced on the second dissociation of the acid, as it nullifies with increase in the carbon chain. In case of methyl malonic and dimethyl malonic, the presence of electron donating methyl group decreases the acidity strength of the carboxylate groups and resulted in the relative higher values of dissociation constants than the parent malonic acid (Table-1).

In the present communication picolinic, quinolinic and dipicolinic are common primary and malic, maleic, chlorosuccinic, dimercapto succinic, methyl malonic and dimethyl malonic acids as secondary ligands. All the ligands form 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with uranyl ion in the pH range 2.0 – 5.5 except maleic, chlorosuccinic

and dimercapto succinic. The co-ordination of UO_2^{2+} with picolinic and dipicolinic is through nitrogen and oxygen of carboxylate group and that of quinolinic acid is through two $-COO^-$ groups^{14,19}. The nature of coordinating atoms for other ligands are similar and observed stability constants are expected by their basicities, ring size and nature of the substituent in the parent acid except dimethyl malonic acid^{9,11}. In fact, higher stability constants should have been obtained in dimethyl malonic than methyl malonic, contrary to this, destabilized nature of these binary bis complexes due to the steric hindrance in dimethyl malonic acid complex, presence of two methyl groups substituted to the same carbon atom to which carboxylic groups bonded.

$-\Delta \log K$ values (Table-2) indicate the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary. The difference in stability between the binary and ternary complexes is a way to characterize the tendency toward formation of ternary complexes with regard to the mixed complexes. It is informative to compare the stability constants of binary complexes with that of ternary. Thus, $\Delta \log K$ is a measure of the affinity that Y has bonding to the aquated metal ion and to the complex (MX). However, in quinolinic-chlorosuccinic acids system, $\Delta \log K = +0.07$ value close to zero, shows the equal tendency of the dianions to coordinate 1:1 UO_2^{2+} -quinolinate complex. In these systems $\Delta \log K$ follow the order with reference to the secondary ligands: methyl malonic > dimethyl malonic > chlorosuccinic/malic > maleic > dimercapto succinic. The K_{DXY} values are close to predicted on statistical consideration in most of the systems studied in the present work. The value 0.02 of K_{DXY} in dipicolinic-dimercaptosuccinic acid system indicates the equal tendency of mixed-ligand formation by disproportionation reaction and dimercapto succinic dianion to bond 1:1 UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinate complex. However, in dipicolinic-malic and dipicolinic-chlorosuccinic acid system, -0.10 and -0.15 values of K_{DXY} point out that these secondary dianions prefer to coordinate to the 1:1 UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinate complex rather than aquated uranyl ion. The significantly higher value of K_{DXY} in quinolinic-chlorosuccinic acid system shows the formation of ternary complex by disproportionation equilibria. Additionally, small positive $\Delta \log K$ in this system indicates that the equilibrium $MX + MY \rightleftharpoons MXY^{2-} + M^{2+}$ is more on right side²⁰.

The values of K_{2XY} and K_{MY_2} point out that the ternary complexes are favoured. A comparison of K_{2YX} values with K_{MX_2} especially in the systems involving malic, methyl malonic and dimethyl malonic as secondary ligands reveals the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary. The order of K_{2YX} and ΣpK with reference to secondary ligand is :

- i) dimercapto succinic > chlorosuccinic > maleic > malic > dimethyl malonic > methyl malonic
- ii) methyl malonic > dimethyl malonic > malic > maleic > chlorosuccinic > dimercaptosuccinic.

TABLE 2—LOGARITHMS OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF UO_2^{2+} -PYRIDINE CARBOXYLIC (Y)-SECONDARY (X) ACID SYSTEMS.

system/acid	Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ C$				
	β_{XY}^*	K_{DXY}^a	K_{2XY}	K_{1YX}	$\Delta \log K$
picolinic-malic	9.53 (2)	0.86	5.07	4.03	-0.43
picolinic-maleic	9.22 (3)	0.32 ^b	4.76	4.07	-0.39
picolinic-chlorosuccinic	7.51 (1)	0.19 ^b	3.05	3.94	-0.52
picolinic-dimercaptosuccinic	7.16 (4)	0.36 ^b	2.70	4.10	-0.36
picolinic-methylmalonic	9.92 (2)	0.35	5.46	3.22	-1.24
picolinic-dimethylmalonic	9.74 (1)	0.46	5.28	3.44	-1.04
Quinolinic-malic	9.58 (5)	0.86	4.93	4.08	-0.57
Quinolinic-maleic	9.26 (4)	0.46 ^b	4.61	4.11	-0.54
Quinolinic-chlorosuccinic	8.29 (2)	1.07 ^b	3.64	4.72	+0.07
Quinolinic-dimercaptosuccinic	7.27 (3)	0.56 ^b	2.62	4.21	-0.44
Quinolinic-methylmalonic	10.48 (4)	0.87	5.83	3.78	-0.87
Quinolinic-dimethylmalonic	10.25 (2)	0.91	5.60	3.93	-0.72
Dipicolinic-malic	10.41 (2)	0.50	4.97	4.91	-0.53
Dipicolinic-maleic	10.29 (3)	-0.10 ^b	4.85	5.14	-0.30
Dipicolinic-chlorosuccinic	8.66 (2)	-0.15 ^b	3.22	5.09	-0.35
Dipicolinic-dimercaptosuccinic	8.32 (4)	0.02 ^b	2.88	5.26	-0.18
Dipicolinic-methylmalonic	11.73 (3)	0.93	6.29	5.03	-0.41
Dipicolinic-Dimethylmalonic	11.43 (2)	0.90	5.99	5.11	-0.33

* The values given in parentheses are standard deviations.

The formation of ternary complex appears to be mainly dependent on the ring size of the chelate which seems to offset the increasing basicity of the secondary ligands as evident from the inverse relationship between K_{2YX} and the product of acid dissociation constants. We reported the direct relationship between these two quantities for the mixed-ligand complexes of vanadyl and neodymium ion with phenolic and carboxylic acids^{7,14}. However, Santappa *et al.* have shown the inverse and direct relationship between these two quantities for ternary complexes of uranyl ion with carboxylic acids^{10,11}. In the present work, the plot of

K_{2YX} vs ΣpK (Fig. 1) gave inverse relationship for the series of closely related secondary ligands. Despite of the highest value of product of the acid dissociation constants in dimethyl malonic acid, however, the points corresponding to the systems involving this acid as secondary ligand deviated from the straight line. Destabilized nature of the ternary complexes has been attributed to the fact that the presence of two methyl groups in dimethyl malonic acid cause the steric hindrance in the ternary complexes. The effect is same in the ternary complexes, as evidently shown in the binary bis complexes also (Table-1).

Fig. 1 Relation between K_{2YX} and the product of acid dissociation constants of the ligands for uranyl ion-pyridine carboxylic-dibasic acid systems: (a) uranyl ion-picolinic-ligands, (b) uranyl ion-quinolinic-ligands and (c) uranyl-ion-dipicolinic-ligands. Ligands: (1) malic, (2) Maleic, (3) chlorosuccinic, (4) dimercaptosuccinic, (5) methyl malonic, and (6) dimethylmalonic.

$\mu=0.1 M(\text{NaClO}_2)$, $t=30^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 2 Relation between β_{XY} and K_{MX_1} for ternary complexes of uranyl ion-pyridine carboxylic-secondary ligands. (a) uranyl ion-picolinic-ligands, (b) uranyl ion-quinolinic-ligands, and (c) uranyl-ion-dipicolinic-ligands. Ligands: (1) malic, (2) maleic, (3) chlorosuccinic, (4) dimercaptosuccinic, (5) methyl malonic and (6) dimethylmalonic.

$\mu=0.1 M(\text{NaClO}_4)$, $t=30^\circ\text{C}$

The overall stabilities (β_{XY}) follow the order: methyl malonic > dimethyl malonic > malic > maleic > chloro succinic > dimercapto succinic. This is in accordance with 1:1 binary stabilities with reference to the secondary ligands. The plots of β_{XY} vs. K_{MX_1} (Fig. 2) exhibit the linear relationship.

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